

“NATIONAL CULTURAL PASSPORT” AS A GAMIFICATION TOOL IN FORMING NATIONAL VALUES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN: EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

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Abstract

Abstract. The article analyzes the pedagogical potential of the gamification approach in forming national values among preschool-age children, using the «National Cultural Passport» tool as a case study. The problem is identified as traditional national upbringing being conducted at the «general group» level, with limited opportunities for continuously monitoring the development of individual children. The «National Cultural Passport» is substantiated as an individual portfolio-monitoring tool based on gamification mechanics such as progress (the gradual filling of pages), achievement badges, and self-monitoring. The results of experimental work carried out in 2024-2026 at two preschool education institutions in the Fergana region (96 children in total) are presented. The results confirm the diagnostic and motivational effectiveness of the tool: in the experimental group, the proportion of children actively filling in the passport rose from 12 percent to 93 percent, while the indicator of active participation in national games increased by 52 percentage points.

Keywords

preschool education, national values, gamification, ethnopedagogy, national cultural passport, national games, experimental study, national identity.

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA MILLIY QADRIYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA “MILLIY MADANIY PASPORT” GAMIFIKATSIYA VOSITASI: TAJRIBA-SINOV NATIJALARI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalarda milliy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda gamifikatsiya yondashuvining pedagogik imkoniyatlari

“Milliy madaniy pasport” vositasi misolida tahlil etiladi. An’anaviy milliy tarbiya “umumiy guruh” darajasida olib borilishi va alohida bolaning rivojlanishini uzluksiz kuzatish imkoniyatining cheklanganligi muammo sifatida ko‘rsatiladi. “Milliy madaniy pasport” - progress (sahifaning to‘ldirib borishi), yutuq belgilari va o‘z-o‘zini kuzatish kabi gamifikatsiya mexanikalariga asoslangan individual portfolio-kuzatuv vositasi sifatida asoslanadi. 2024-2026-yillarda Farg‘ona viloyatining ikkita maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotida (jami 96 nafar bola) o‘tkazilgan tajriba-sinov ishlari natijalari taqdim etiladi. Natijalar vositaning diagnostik va motivatsion samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi: tajriba guruhida pasportni faol to‘ldirgan bolalar ulushi 12 foizdan 93 foizgacha o‘sgan, milliy o‘yinlarda faol ishtirok ko‘rsatkichi esa 52 foiz punktga ortgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: maktabgacha ta’lim, milliy qadriyatlar, gamifikatsiya, etnopedagogika, milliy madaniy pasport, milliy o‘yinlar, tajriba-sinov, milliy identitet.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются педагогические возможности подхода геймификации в формировании национальных ценностей у детей дошкольного возраста на примере инструмента «Национальный культурный паспорт». В качестве проблемы указывается то, что традиционное национальное воспитание проводится на уровне «общей группы» и возможности непрерывного наблюдения за развитием отдельного ребёнка ограничены. «Национальный культурный паспорт» обосновывается как индивидуальный инструмент портфолио-наблюдения, основанный на таких механиках геймификации, как прогресс (постепенное заполнение страниц), значки достижений и самонаблюдение. Представлены результаты опытно-экспериментальной работы, проведённой в 2024-2026 годах в двух дошкольных образовательных организациях Ферганской области (всего 96 детей). Результаты подтверждают диагностическую и мотивационную эффективность инструмента: в экспериментальной группе доля детей, активно заполняющих паспорт, выросла с 12 процентов до 93 процентов, а показатель активного участия в национальных играх увеличился на 52 процентных пункта.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, национальные ценности, геймификация, этнопедагогика, национальный культурный паспорт, национальные игры, опытно-экспериментальная работа, национальная идентичность.

Introduction

In the contemporary context of rapidly developing globalization and digital technologies, transmitting national customs, traditions, and values to the younger generation has become one of the pressing tasks of the preschool education system. It is precisely at preschool age that the initial foundations of national consciousness, moral notions, and cultural identity are formed in a child. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Preschool Education and Upbringing,» as well as state programs, define educating the younger generation in the spirit of national values as a priority direction.

However, in practice, the systematic use of national customs, values, and traditions as a pedagogical tool has still not been fully established: they are often limited to formal holiday events. Moreover, in traditional practice, national upbringing is conducted mainly at the «general group» level, meaning it is not visible in which area an individual child is ahead and in which they are falling behind. This contradiction necessitates the search for new pedagogical tools that make it possible to continuously monitor and encourage the national development of each child.

In recent years, gamification - that is, the approach of introducing game elements (progress, points, levels, achievement badges, self-monitoring) into non-game processes - has become widespread in pedagogy. The aim of this article is to substantiate the «National Cultural Passport» tool from the perspective of gamification and to demonstrate, on the basis of empirical data, its effectiveness in forming national values among preschool-age children.

Literature Review

The theoretical foundations of educating preschool-age children on the basis of national values have been extensively studied by Uzbek scholars K. Hoshimov, S.

Nishonova, D.Sh. Mirzayeva, F.R. Qodirova, as well as researchers M. Quronov, O. Hasanboyeva, and others. G.N. Volkov, the founder of world ethnopedagogy, defined folk pedagogy as the educational experience accumulated by a people over centuries. In explaining the psychological mechanisms of child upbringing, L. Kohlberg's theory of moral development and J. Piaget's theory of cognitive development serve as important methodological foundations: a preschool-age child learns not through abstract concepts but through direct observation, feeling, and imitation.

Gamification theory (S. Deterding and others) and self-determination theory show that seeing progress, celebrating small achievements, and monitoring one's own results significantly increase a child's motivation. At the same time, in existing research, ethnopedagogical heritage and gamification mechanics are poorly linked, especially in the preschool education context. It is precisely this gap that defines the novelty of this study: conveying traditional national values to the child through a gamified individual monitoring tool.

Research Methodology

The experimental work was carried out during 2024-2026 at two preschool education institutions (PEIs) in the Fergana region. The first was PEI No. 63 in the city of Fergana (urban setting, 50 children involved in the experiment), and the second was PEI No. 23 in the Fergana district (rural setting, 46 children). A total of 96 children participated in the study. In both institutions, the groups were divided into an experimental group (EG) and a control group (CG); in the experimental group, the «National Cultural Passport» and other innovative methods were applied, while in the control group the usual program was continued. Initial diagnostics confirmed that there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

The study was carried out in four stages: preparation and initial diagnostics (Q3 of 2024); the main experiment (Q4 of 2024 - Q4 of 2025, 18 months); final diagnostics and analysis (Q1 of 2026); and the generalization of methodological recommendations. To assess effectiveness, tools such as an observation protocol, a picture test, the «Who

Am I?» projective methodology, pedagogical interviews, and a questionnaire for parents were used.

The «National Cultural Passport» as a Gamification Tool

The «National Cultural Passport» is an individual portfolio-monitoring tool that is opened for each child and filled in throughout the academic year. The «passport» consists of five pages, each dedicated to a specific area of national values: «National Games I Know», «Fairy Tales and Lullabies I Have Heard», «National Objects I Recognize», «National Holidays I Have Attended», and «My Family's Traditions». Whenever a child learns a new game, hears a new fairy tale, or attends a holiday, they place a small mark - a drawing, a sticker, or a handprint - on the relevant page.

From a pedagogical perspective, this tool is based on clear gamification mechanics. First, progress: the gradual filling of the pages displays the child's achievement in a visible form. Second, achievement badges (stickers, handprints) - this is a child-friendly version of the classic «badge» system. Third, self-monitoring: because the passport is filled in by the child themselves, it serves not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a powerful internal motivational factor. In this way, the tool aligns with the theories of L. Kohlberg and J. Piaget: a preschool-age child perceives not an abstract value but a visible, tangible result.

Research Results and Their Analysis

The data obtained at the end of the eighteen-month experiment showed a consistent picture: in the experimental groups, significant growth was observed across all five indicators; growth also occurred in the control group, but at a considerably lower rate. Table 1 below presents a comparative analysis of the indicators of the experimental and control groups.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of the indicators of the experimental (EG) and control (CG) groups

<i>Indicator</i>	EG	EG	CG	EG
	before, %	after, %	after, %	growth, pp
<i>Active participation in</i>	44	96	64	+52

<i>national games</i>				
<i>Knowledge of national values</i>	36	86	52	+50
<i>Expressing values in speech</i>	30	78	44	+48
<i>Parental involvement</i>	41	87	55	+46
<i>Sense of national belonging</i>	38	82	49	+44

Several key conclusions follow from Table 1. The largest growth was recorded in the indicator of active participation in national games (+52 percentage points) - this is understandable, since national games are the most engaging area for children, and the gamified passport encouraged them to record their participation. In terms of knowledge of national values, the experimental group showed a result 34 percentage points higher than the control group, which confirms that the gamified approach is significantly more effective than traditional methods. Parental involvement also increased significantly (+46 pp), since the process of filling in the passport also engaged the family.

The direct impact of the «National Cultural Passport» tool is clearly visible in the dynamics of its completion. In the experimental group, the proportion of children who actively filled in the passport rose from 12 percent in September to 93 percent by May; in the control group, where a traditional observation notebook was used, this indicator remained at 44 percent. The sharpest jump coincided with March - the Navruz period: pre-holiday events allowed children to fill in several pages of the passport at once. This indicator confirms that the tool has not only a diagnostic but also a powerful motivational effect - that is, the progress and achievement mechanics of gamification produce real results.

Figure 1. Nine-month completion dynamics of the «National Cultural Passport» (EG and CG, %)

The quantitative results were also reinforced by qualitative analysis. At PEI No. 63, after a potter from Rishton showed the children how to make a bowl from clay, three days later, during free play, one girl made a bowl from plasticine and told her friends, «I am a potter» - this was a child from an urban family whose parents were not potters. At PEI No. 23, in the «Who Am I?» diagnostics, a six-year-old child described themselves as a «Fergana Uzbek child,» through the Navruz tradition in the neighborhood and planting a poplar tree together with their father - a year earlier, the same child had referred to themselves simply as «a child.» In these responses, the cognitive, affective, and behavioral layers of national identity manifested simultaneously.

A comparative analysis of the urban (PEI No. 63) and district (PEI No. 23) preschool education institutions showed that the difference in initial indicators was minimal. This was a somewhat unexpected result, since there had been an assumption that traditions are better preserved in rural families; while practice did confirm that traditions are more preserved in rural areas, it showed that this knowledge is also not equally systematic. Therefore, a gamified, systematic tool is necessary in both environments.

Conclusion

The experimental results confirmed the high effectiveness of the «National Cultural Passport» tool in forming national values among preschool-age children. Based on the gamification mechanics of progress, achievement badges, and self-monitoring, the tool raises national upbringing from the «general group» level to the individual level of each child. The increase in the proportion of children actively filling in the passport from 12 percent to 93 percent, as well as the rise in active participation in national games by 52 percentage points, demonstrates both the diagnostic and motivational value of the tool.

Most importantly, the study showed that improving the quality of national upbringing does not require large financial expenditures or complex technology: the «National Cultural Passport» is a thick notebook, colored pencils, and the educator's

systematic approach. The tool is simple, inexpensive, and can be applied in any preschool education institution. In future research, converting the passport tool into a digital (mobile application) format and analyzing the results with expanded statistical methods (t-test, confidence level) are considered promising directions.

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